

An Analytical Study To Understand The Impact Of Hybrid Work Culture On Productivity Of It Organization Employees

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Cite this paper as: Deepali Sonawane and Dr. Irfan Siddiqui (2024). An Analytical Study To Understand The Impact Of Hybrid Work Culture On Productivity Of It Organization Employees. Frontiers in Health Informatics, Vol. 13, No.8, 7827-7833

ABSTRACT

The study aims to understand impact of hybrid work culture on productivity of IT organization employees. Employee productivity depends on various key factors while working in hybrid work system. Most of the organization start implementing hybrid work model after COVID-19. Hybrid work system which is combination of remote and on-site work become the integral part of IT organization. Hybrid work model enhances the flexibility and performance of employee. This research study investigates that various factors like work-life balance, flexibility, technological infrastructure, leadership support, communication and organization policies influence productivity of employee. A structured questionnaire was shared to IT employees across various organizations in Maharashtra. The collected data were analysed using descriptive statistics and percentage analysis. The result of analysis says that flexibility in work arrangement, supportive leadership and robust technological infrastructure play very important role in the improvement of productivity and satisfaction of employee. However, some challenges are observed while working in Hybrid Work System such as communication barriers, inconsistent hybrid work policies etc. The study concludes that a well-structured hybrid work model improves the productivity of employee. The finding provides valuable insights for management professionals in implementing hybrid work system that align with both organizational goals and employee well-being.

Keywords: Hybrid work culture, Employee Productivity, Work-life balance, IT organization

INTRODUCTION

In recent years, the way employee work has changed a lot. The change in the traditional on-site work system to remote work system in the organizations after COVID-19 pandemic. Many organizations had to quickly adopt new ways of working to keep their operations running and take care of their employees' health and safety. Especially IT organizations are using hybrid work model. Hybrid work model is the combination of onsite work and off-site work. Hybrid work model allows employees to work on-site for some days and work off-site for other days. This model provides flexibility to employees to manage their work as per their convenient time. This model has become especially useful for the Information Technology organizations, where technology driven operations allow for seamless collaboration across locations.

Fig. 1: Hybrid Work Model

<https://www.corexta.com/wp-content/uploads/2025/04/What-Is-Hybrid-Work.png>

Employee productivity plays a very important role in an organization's growth, so it is necessary to understand how hybrid work model affects employee productivity. Hybrid work model provides flexibility, saves time and cost of employees. Employees feel less stressed and more satisfied when they can choose where and how to work. However, this system also comes with challenges. Sometimes coordination becomes difficult when employees work from different places. Communication between team members may not always be smooth. Team leader may also find it harder to monitor and support employees effectively. Keeping employee motivated and engaged can be a challenge in hybrid work system. Organization use multiple tools that increase cyber risks like data phishing, data breaches as employees are working from different locations.

The study focuses on understanding different factors such as work-life balance, flexibility, leadership support, technology and communication affect the employee productivity in hybrid work system. By analysing IT organization employee experiences those who are working in hybrid mode, the research finds that which factors affect the employee productivity. The objective of this study is to provide useful insights that can help organizations to implement better hybrid work model. When organizations understand what factors increase or decrease productivity of employee, they can take the right steps to create a balance between performance and flexibility. The finding of this study will help team leaders, managers, HR professionals, policy makers to develop more effective and sustainable hybrid work model. In long run, these insights can contribute to improve employee performance, satisfaction, organization efficiency and overall business success.

Fig. 2: Relationship between Hybrid Work Culture (Dependent Variable) and Employee Productivity (Independent Variable)

OBJECTIVES

1. To identify the key factors which are influencing the productivity of employee while working in hybrid work culture.
2. To analyse the relationship between independent variable i.e. hybrid work system and dependent variable employee productivity.
3. To determine the role of work-life balance, digital technology, communication and leadership in enhancing productivity.
4. To find the challenges faced by employees in hybrid work model.
5. To suggest the best practices to improve employee productivity in hybrid work environment.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The research methodology follows the systematic way to achieve the objectives of the research study and to ensure the accuracy and reliability of findings. This analytical study focuses on to understand the effect of hybrid work system on productivity of employee within IT organization in Maharashtra.

1. **Research Design:** The research study follows the analytical and destructive research design. Descriptive research is used to understand existing pattern and perceptions regarding hybrid work system. While analytical methods are used to interpret the data collection and find the relationship between dependent and independent variables. In this study hybrid work system is independent variable whereas employee productivity is the dependent variable.
2. **Population:** In the study population is employees which are working in IT organization with hybrid work system across Maharashtra. A total 150 responses were collected from employees using convenience sampling. Efforts were made to include participants across various employment levels and genders to ensure the sample was a reasonable representation of the target population.
3. **Sample:** Out of 150 responses, 43 responses were invalid therefore excluded from the data

analysis. As a result, final data set of 107 valid responses were used for data analysis. Using convenience sampling 107 responses was selected for data analysis, so the sample size is 107 for the research study.

4. **Data Collection:** Primary data is used for data analysis. Data collected through a structured questionnaire. Questionnaire designed on 5-point Likert scale as Strongly agree, agree, neutral, disagree, strongly disagree.
5. **Data Analysis:** The 107 records were used for data analysis. Data were analysed using descriptive method and using percentage analysis. Data visualization done using Tableau software. Tables and Graphs were used for data representation and interpretation of result.

Table 1: Section wise responses received from employees

Sr. No.	Section	Strongly Agree (%)	Agree (%)	Neutral (%)	Disagree (%)	Strongly Disagree (%)
1	Factors influencing productivity	40	40	17	6	1
2	Relationship between hybrid work and productivity	34	43	21	6	1
3	Benefits of Hybrid work culture	42	36	19	6	2
4	Challenges in hybrid work	15	29	30	23	7
5	Best practices for hybrid work system	38	48	15	2	0

Columns	Section	Measure Names
Rows	Measure Values	

Section wise responses received from employees

Fig. 3: Section wise responses received from employees

The responses were categorized under five sections as follows.

- i. Factors influencing productivity
- ii. Relationship between hybrid work and productivity
- iii. Benefits of hybrid work culture
- iv. Challenges in hybrid work
- v. Best practices for hybrid work system

The Tableau software used to draw horizontal bar chart in above illustrates the distribution of responses across these sections.

- i. **Factors influencing Productivity:** The majority of respondents, 40% strongly agree and 40% agree believed that hybrid work culture positively influences productivity by improving satisfaction, motivation and communication. Only 7% respondents are in disagree mode.
- ii. **Relationship Between Hybrid Work and Productivity:** In this section, strongly agreed and agreed combined responses are 77%. These responses shows that hybrid work system enhances employees task efficiency as well as employees work quality. These responses also indicate a strong link between hybrid work model and employee's productivity.
- iii. **Benefits of Hybrid Work Culture:** In this section, strongly agreed and agreed combined responses are 78%. These responses shows that hybrid work system has benefits such as flexibility, work-life balance and leadership support. These responses indicates that hybrid work system provides higher employees job satisfaction and employees are more focused.
- iv. **Challenges in Hybrid Work Culture:** For this section responses are in mixed opinion. 44% respondents are agreed for challenge existence where as 56% are as in neutral or disagree for the challenges in Hybrid Work culture. This results that challenges included communication barriers, inconsistencies in policy and lack of interaction.
- v. **Best Practices for Hybrid Work System:** This section shows that 86% respondents agreed for best practices which are used in hybrid work system. Respondents are agreed for clear policies, regular virtual meetings and use of digital technology which increase the coordination and employee productivity. The 14% responses are disagreed and shows strong consensus on the importance of structured hybrid work policies.

INTERPRETATION

The research study indicates that hybrid work model plays very important role to increase the employee productivity. Work flexibility, effective leadership, work life balance and advanced technology are the benefits of hybrid work model. Due to these benefits employee has greater job satisfaction and provide better performance. However, organizations face some challenges in ensuring consistent communication, maintaining team collaboration and establishing clear policies for hybrid work system. Despite these challenges, most of the employees agreed for hybrid work model. They are agreed for hybrid work model as a beneficial and sustainable model which increase the productivity and wellbeing of employee. While implementing hybrid work model in organization, they should follow structured communication method, efficient communication channels and transparent organizational practices.

FINDINGS:

Following are the key findings from data analysis and interpretation.

1. **Positive influence on productivity:** A majority respondents agreed that hybrid work culture

has improved their overall productivity and job satisfaction. Hybrid work system environment enables employees to perform tasks more efficiently and maintain focus.

2. **Enhance Work-life balance:** Most of the employees were agreed for hybrid work model provides balanced personal and professional work. The major advantage of hybrid work model is flexibility in work which contributes significantly to reduce stress of employees and improve the mental health of employees.
3. **Importance of Digital Technology and leadership:** Employees get reliable technological infrastructure while working in hybrid work model. Employees can use different digital tools while working from remote places. Supportive leadership is also important for hybrid work system. Employees with proper access of digital tools and timely guidance from supervisors' results in higher efficiency.
4. **Challenges in Hybrid Work System:** Some employees face difficulties in coordination, communication and maintaining balance between personal and professional life. Technical issues and inconsistent policies of hybrid work are also challenges for affecting employee's performance.
5. **Clear Policies and structured framework:** Respondents strongly agreed for well- defined hybrid work policies, regular virtual meetings and performance evaluations based on outcomes rather than presence are essential for sustained productivity.

CONCLUSION

The conclusion of research study is hybrid work culture has a positive influence on productivity of employee, especially in IT organization. The data analysis clearly indicates that flexibility, effective leadership and technological support are the main factors of enhanced performance in hybrid work system. Due to flexibility feature, employees are able to manage their work schedules. This results in improved focus, motivation to employees and overall job satisfaction. However, the research study also highlights some challenges such as inconsistent communication, lack of policy clarity and technical issues. Despite these issues, the majority of employees perceive hybrid work as an efficient and sustainable work model. This model aligns organizational objectives with employee well-being. In summary, we can say that the hybrid work system is strategic evolution of the modern workplace, offering organizations a competitive advantage when implemented effectively.

SUGGESTIONS

Following are the suggestions proposed to improve the effectiveness of hybrid work system.

1. **Develop Clear and Consistent Hybrid Work Policies:** Organizations should establish well defined guidelines which includes work schedules, performance evaluation and communication expectation.
2. **Enhance Technical Infrastructure:** Continuous investment in reliable digital tools, cyber security and connectivity is important.
3. **Promote Leadership and Managerial Support:** Team leader and management leaders should ensure regular interaction with employees, timely feedback and recognition to keep employee engaged and motivated.
4. **Work Life Balance Encouragement:** Employees should promote flexible scheduling and wellness that initiatives to maintain long term productivity.
5. **Strengthen Communication Channels:** Regular virtual meetings, collaborative platforms and transparent reporting systems can reduce communication gap and enhance coordination.

6. **Focus on Outcome-based performance evaluation:** Productivity should be assessed on results and contributions rather than physical presence in the office.
7. **Training and Skill Development:** Learning programs and workshops on hybrid work practices can improve adaptability and efficiency among employees.

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